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Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic Related lockdown: Present and Future

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Chemistry of Covid-19 Associated in Pandemic Context

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Abstract -

Research and development has play crucial role to fight against the global epidemic situation created by COVID-19. Most of the core chemistry based research organization and pharmaceutical companies are accompanying their efforts towards collecting more and more information about the Corona virus, evolving improved testing tools, and sooner or later creating a vaccine. In the current time we are in need of quick and more effective screening technique for the quick diagnosis of disease. In this review article we explain the origin, chemical aspect of virus, its prevention using the shield of Chemistry and upcoming future possibilities in research. Chemistry is an important aspect at every step at battle against Corona virus pandemic.

Keywords - Covid-19, Role of chemistry, Preventive measures

Introduction -

Since many people worldwide are now keenly aware, a COVID-19 outbreak was identified in the last month of 2019 in mainland China. Because of this date, this extremely infectious illness has impacted every continent in the world, with nearly one million patients reported in more than two hundred countries worldwide. A novel coronavirus was reported in China in late December 2019 which caused severe respiratory viral infection including pneumonia. This was first detected in Wuhan, China in December-2019 and has subsequently spread around the globe, contributing to an ongoing pandemic [1-2]. It had been originally named Novel Coronavirus and the World Health Organization (WHO) stated the virus-related syntax elsewhere [3]. The virus that caused the infection was named-severe acute respiratory coronavirus 2 syndrome (SARS-CoV-2). The disease induced by infection is called coronavirus or COVID-19 disease. COVID-19 was listed as an Infectious High-Consequence Infection Outbreak. Coronavirus

disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a contagious infection that is caused by coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), an extreme acute respiratory syndrome [4]. The earliest reported cases were linked to a large market for seafood and animals in Wuhan, suggesting an initial animal to person Disseminate. However, a growing numbers of subsequent patients did not introduce themselves to animal markets, signifying from one human to another spread. This is focused on what was historically known as MERS coronavirus incubation time. It is likely that early alienation, treatment and management is mutual contributing to substantial mortality [5-6]. In fact, health-care workers attenuation a consequence of concentrated research management may also lead to higher mortality rates. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has been declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization [7]. A comprehensive community effort is needed to stop the virus from spreading any further. A pandemic is defined as which occurs over a wide geographic area and affects an exceptionally high proportion of the population [8]. The last pandemic reported in the world was the 2009 H1N1 swine-flu pandemic. In this context, this article appraised the role of chemistry in the present circumstances on COVID-19.

COVID-19 -

Coronaviruses are a genus of viruses that cause diseases such as respiratory or gastrointestinal illness. Respiratory diseases can vary from common cold to more serious illnesses, such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV) and Extreme Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV). A novel coronavirus (nCoV) is a modern strain previously unrecognized in humans. Once scientists identify exactly what coronavirus it is, they give it a name COVID-19 case, SARS-CoV-2 is the virus that causes it. Corona viruses received their name from the tiny

way they appear. The virus consists of a nucleus of genetic material enclosed by a protein-spiked shell which makes the crown appearance. In Latin the term Corona means "CROWN". The coronaviruses are zoonotic which means the viruses are transmitted between humans and animals [9-10]. Infection of COVID-19 disease occur the common and severe symptoms are given in the diagrammatically as shown in the figure-1;

Figure-1: COVID-19 disease common and severe symptoms [11]

Corona virus disease (COVID-19) is a recently identified coronavirus-caused infectious disease. Many patients with COVID-19 who get sick should have mild to moderate symptoms and heal without any care. How it spreads the virus that triggers COVID-19 is transmitted mainly through droplets that are produced when an infected individual coughs, sneezes or exhales. These droplets are too large to stay in the breeze, on floors or surfaces easily when the person are next to someone who has COVID-19 or touching a contaminated surface and then the eyes, nose or mouth, the individual may be affected by breathing in the virus [12].

Role of Chemistry for Prevention of COVID-19 -

1) **Chemical Means** - There are four ways to destroy corona virus [13] is diagrammatically discussed in the table-1 given below;

Methods	Reasons
<p>1. DISINFECTANT</p> <p>Hand washing with soap for 20 seconds makes away the viruses and bacteria and also remove the dirt and grease.</p>	<p>Soap molecules dissolve the lipid outside layer of the corona virus. Any kind of soap or surfactant is effective to break the outer layer of virus.</p>
<p>2. ALCOHOL HAND SANITISER</p> <p>70% ALCOHOL (MINIMUM 60% CONCENTRATION)</p>	<p>Alcohol molecules dissolve the fatty outer layer of the corona virus and damage the protein structure of virus. About 60-70% alcohol content is used in hand sanitizers.</p>
<p>3. BLEACH SOLUTION</p> <p>5% BLEACH</p> <p>MINIMUM CONCENTRATION OF 0.5% HYPOCHLORITE</p>	<p>Bleach oxidizes and destroys the virus proteins and genetic material. It should be left on the surface for at least 10 to 15 minutes.</p>
<p>4. HYDROGEN PEROXIDE</p> <p>H₂O₂</p> <p>MINIMUM CONCENTRATION OF 6% HYDROGEN PEROXIDE</p>	<p>Hydrogen peroxide oxidizes and destroys the virus proteins and genetic material. It should be left on the surface for at least 10 to 15 minutes.</p>

2) **Medicinal and Clinical Means** - Currently, it is satisfying to find out that there are at least four appropriate forms of chemicals

displayed good antiviral capacity that was allowed in clinics to combat the disease according to The Sixth COVID-19 Protocol version in China, 3CLpro targeting lopinavir and ritonavir; RdRp targeting ribavirin, Chloroquine Diphosphate targeting endosomal acidification, arbidol targeting production of 2'-5' oligoadenylates [14]. Lopinavir and ritonavir, in a family of drugs named protease inhibitors, also target non-structural SARS-CoV 3CLpro protein, approved by FDA in 2000 [15]. Ribavirin is an FDA authorized antiviral prescription drug that is often used in conjunction with other pharmaceutical substances management of recurrent hepatitis C virus and hemorrhagic virus fevers [16]. Ribavirin is a synthetic guanosine nucleoside against many RNA and DNA viruses that interferes with the synthesis of RdRp targeting viral mRNA introduced in medicine in the 1940s, chloroquine is a part of a significant group of chemically associated antimalarials, certain derivatives of quinoline. Chloroquine phosphate is orally treated as a source of chloroquine. Phosphate in chloroquine locates a family of medicines labeled antimalarial and amebicides that are used for malaria prevention and diagnosis. China, researchers from the Wuhan Institute of Virology measured chloroquine antiviral effectiveness against a clinical nCoV 2019 isolate in vitro was considered to be significantly successful in managing 2019-nCoV infection [17-18]. The structures of the above discussed compounds are given below;

Figure-3: Satisfying chemical drugs are used to cure COVID-19

Summary -

In the above discussion, it can be concluded and suggested that the virus is primarily transmitted among people during close contact, most often through small droplets formed by coughing, sneezing, and talking. The droplets typically fall to the ground or to surfaces, rather than traveling long distances by air. Supported contagion control steps involve regular hand washing, preserving physical

distance from others particularly from those having symptoms, quarantine particularly for those have symptoms, covering cough and holding unwashed hands away from the nose. Recommendations for face covering use by the general public differ, with some agencies advising against them, others advocating against them, and others allowing their use. No evidence exists both for and against the use of face masks of healthy individuals in the bigger community. There are neither vaccines available nor specific antiviral treatments presently available for COVID-19, according to the World Health Organization.

References -

- Hui D.S., I Azhar E, Madani T.A., Ntoumi F., Kock R., Dar O., The continuing 2019-nCoV epidemic threat of novel coronaviruses to global health - The latest 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China, *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 91: 264-266, (Feb-2020), doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2020.01.009.
- WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19, World Health Organization (WHO) Press release, (March-2020).
- <https://icmanaesthesiacovid-19.org/background>
- Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)-Symptoms and causes, Mayo Clinic. Retrieved, (April 2020)
- Li, Q.; Guan, X.; Wu, P.; Wang, X.; Zhou, L.; Tong, Y.; Ren, R.; Leung, K.S.; Lau, E.H.; Wong, J.Y. Early transmission dynamics in Wuhan, China, of novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia. *New England J. Med.*, (2020)
- Guan, W.-J.; Ni, Z.-Y.; Hu, Y.; Liang, W.-H.; Ou, C.-Q.; He, J.-X.; Liu, L.; Shan, H.; Lei, C.-l.; Hui, D.S. Clinical characteristics of 2019 novel coronavirus infection in China. medRxiv, (2020)
- World Health Organization, WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19, (March 2020). <https://www.who.int/dg/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19—11-march-2020>
- Merriam Webster Dictionary, Pandemic, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/pandemic> (March 2020)
- World Health Organization, Coronavirus, <https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus> (March 2020)
- Chan J.F., Lau S.K., To K.K., Cheng V.C., Woo P.C., Yuen K.Y., Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus: another zoonotic beta-coronavirus causing SARS-like disease, *Clinical microbiology reviews*, 28(2):465-522 (2015) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coronavirus_disease_2019#/media/File:Symptoms_of_coronavirus_disease_2019_4.0.svg
- Public Health England, COVID-19: epidemiology, virology and clinical features, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/wuhan-novel-coronavirus-background-information/wuhan-novel-coronavirus-epidemiology-virology-and-clinical-features>, (March 2020)
- <https://www.compoundchem.com/tag/coronavirus/>
- Li, G.; De Clercq, E. Therapeutic options for the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). *Nature*, (2020)
- Laguno, M.; Murillas, J.; Blanco, J.L.; Martínez, E.; Miquel, R.; Sánchez-Tapias, J.M.; Bargallo, X.; García-Criado, A.; de Lazzari, E.; Larrousse, M. Peginterferon alfa-2b plus ribavirin compared with interferon alfa-2b plus ribavirin for treatment of HIV/HCV co-infected patients. *Aids*, 18(13),27-36, (2004)
- Goswami, B.B.; Borek, E.; Sharma, O.K.; Fujitaki, J.; Smith, R.A. The broad spectrum antiviral agent ribavirin inhibits capping of mRNA. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Co.*, 89(3), 830-836, (1979)
- Wang, M.; Cao, R.; Zhang, L.; Yang, X.; Liu, J.; Xu, M.; Shi, Z.; Hu, Z.; Zhong, W.; Xiao, G. Remdesivir and chloroquine effectively inhibit the recently emerged novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in vitro. *Cell Res.*, 1-3 (2020)
- Wei Liu, Hai-liang Zhu and Yongtao Duan, Effective Chemicals against Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) in China, *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry*, 20, 1-3, (2020)

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